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P(ISSN) : 3007-0031

E(ISSN) : 3007-004X

<https://rc-archive.com/index.php/Journal/about>

Securitization And Development In Pakistan: Priorities And Challenges

Dr Kashif Hussain

Civil servant in the government of Pakistan
Email: khussai4@myune.edu.au

Haider Abbas

Civil servant in the government of Pakistan
Email: haiderabbasgg@gmail.com

Sadia Haider

Civil servant in the government of Pakistan
Email: sadiahaiderr@gmail.com

Publisher : EDUCATION GENIUS SOLUTIONS

Review Type: Double Blind Peer Review

ABSTRACT

It is widely believed that Allah, America and the Army influence policymaking in Pakistan. Article 19 of the Constitution forbids free speech when it comes to the glory of Islam, the integrity, security or defense of Pakistan and friendly relations with foreign States. This shows the influence of these elements, making the nation-building and the identification with indigenous institutions to govern its public difficult. This paper explains Pakistan's developmental challenges by considering the economic, social, and political dynamics. This paper offers a detailed analysis of the application of the theory of securitisation, and development by the state, and the external challenges it faces. This paper highlights the state of internal security and an in-depth analysis of the fragmentation of internal security that causes the rise in extremism.

Keywords: Pakistan, Development, Securitization, Developmental Challenges

Introduction

With the decline of state institutions in many countries and ineffective institutions failing to support development, non-state actors, often violence-prone, step in to create an alternative system of governance, justice, security, and public services (Iannaccone and Berman 2006). This situation further adds to the weakness of the writ of the state. Further, with internal violence ensuing and governments losing their legitimacy and monopoly of violence and service delivery, with crumbling credibility, they cannot provide essential political services such as education, healthcare, and secure financial institutions to their populace (WB 2018). Strong states effectively deliver these services, while weak states offer them to a limited extent. On the other hand, failed states struggle to provide essential services.

Pakistan faces a broad range of developmental issues. Development is an "all-encompassing endeavour that results in better education and higher literacy, adequate healthcare, productive jobs and livelihoods, an acceptable level of nutrition and access to clean drinking water, electricity, roads, and infrastructure for ordinary citizens" (Husain 2018, xiii). According to Myrdal (1968), the development encompasses more than economic progress and improved living conditions. He suggests that human potential must be realized through increased access to commodities and services, higher literacy rates, improved healthcare systems, and freedom from poverty, famine, and social injustices (Myrdal 1968). This begs the question how has this been handled in Pakistan?

Many variables influence how Pakistanis perceive their national identity, the state's role, and an ideal society. Since independence, regardless of their nature and type, these issues are mainly due to interest-based policies. This interest-based policy formulation and lack of a broader consensus on prioritizing sectors for development has led to further aggravation of state affairs. There have been many instances where countries have utilized their natural resources unchecked, benefitting only the elites and adopting an uneven developmental progress that did not reach the grassroots, leading to the country stagnating (Acemoglu and Robinson 2019), where the economy, human development, and social mobility become unstable (Acemoglu and Robinson 2012). Such countries have witnessed conflict in the form of civil wars, social upheavals, law and order breakdowns, and often periods of economic depression (Phillips 2022).

Pakistan's history manifests this pattern: her economy has been under pressure due to uncertainties and instability and has uneven and non-vital development priorities; there is highly pronounced income inequality between the classes, and she has been battling through domestic and international conflicts (Hussain 2020). Among Pakistan's challenges to having a successful development plan is the crisis arising from the lack

of an effective governance model (S.A.A. Shah 2020). This crisis has risen due to the selective design, targeting, selection, and implementation of policies. A highly centralized governance system prevents participatory political institutions, gradually eroding the democratic principle of participation, meritocracy, and a professionally inclined civil service (Qazizada and Wani 2020; Parks et al. 2013; Yesilkagit et al. 2024). Looking at the socioeconomic parameters and indices, Pakistan stands in the middle of everything. It has gone from becoming a fast-growing economy in the 1950s to a struggling one facing a default. Pakistan has lost thousands of innocent lives in its fight against terrorism, extremism and insurgency (Haqqani 2020). The statistics give a picture that is both encouraging and disappointing. The average life expectancy in 1951 was forty years; in 2019, it is sixty-five in 2023. The literacy rate has increased from eleven per cent in 1947 to fifty-eight per cent in 2019 (ASER-Pakistan 2019). With the youth bulge, it is alarming that an official 2018 report on primary school enrolments states there were over 22.6 million out-of-school children (OOSC) (GoP 2018). Pakistani citizens spend more than sixty per cent of their income on their health (GoP 2022), which should be covered by free health care or government contributions. The lack of better ranking in the indices is due to an endemic problem of prioritizing the social sector for development. This causes poor health indicators, a high illiteracy rate, inadequate social services, and an inability to provide security to vulnerable sections of society, eventually worsening the security and protection of the citizens (Banuri 1992). The lack of essential services leads to growing civic intolerance and violence, increased corruption and negative perceptions towards the state institutions, and the virtual collapse of society. It has been argued that a social sector development plan encouraging an educated, healthy, skill-based labor force impels productivity and eventually leads to higher economic growth (WB, 2018). Such a virtuous cycle is the key to human development.

Pakistan faces not only infrastructure issues such as the lack of power, clean water, garbage disposal, and ageing structures but also restricted job and economic growth opportunities, in addition to the ongoing conflict. Challenges with infrastructure and a shortage of employment opportunities, particularly for young people, could lead to an increase in violence as individuals may resort to violence to achieve their goals. Studying developmental challenges is vital to counter growing conflict, militancy, and the ascendancy of jihadist elements and groups (Husain 2019b).

This paper touched upon Pakistan's experience through development and the challenges it faced in providing human development. This paper is divided into three distinct sections and the first section provides a theoretical and conceptual overview of securitisation and development theories. The second section overviews the challenges faced on the touchstone of socio-economic development and political ones. The last section provides the application of theories of securitisation and development in context of Pakistan.

Securitisation theory

The securitisation framework, developed by Buzan, Waever and Wilde (1998), posits that security issues are not objective but are socially constructed as security threats through the securitisation processes. The concept of securitisation presented by the Copenhagen school (Buzan et al.) offers a procedural understanding of the social construction of threat and security policies (Huysmans 2002; Ingram, Schneider, and DeLeon 2019; McDonald 2008). These processes involve constructing a shared understanding of what should be considered and collectively responding to a threat (Buzan, Wæver, and De Wilde 1998). Buzan and his colleagues state that security issues are socially constructed through speech acts. When an issue is dramatized and presented

as a matter of supreme priority in security discourse, an agent claims the need for and right to address it through extraordinary means. The contours of securitisation theory encompass the concept of security, the nature of referent objects and the role of security actors (Brauch 2008; Floyd 2021). Referent objects are entities under threat with a legitimate claim for survival, such as states, tribes, and communities. Actors include state, military, political leaders, international organisations, media and non-governmental groups (McDonald 2008; Hirschauer 2019).

Emmers (2004, 4) classifies referent objects into five categories: the state in the context of military security, national sovereignty or ideology in the context of political security, national economies in the context of economic security, collective identities in the context of societal security, and species or habitats in the context of environmental security. In this scenario, the object in question may or may not exist or possess the capacity to address the challenges in ways that decision-makers determine. Declaring a state of emergency effectively follows the invocation of security. Through this declaration, the government asserts its authority to employ any necessary methods to prevent perilous development, essentially taking extraordinary measures. As a result, utilizing security to justify using force as a means for the state to mobilize or assume special powers constitutes the implementation of extraordinary measures. However, the securitisation of an issue only occurs when the audience accepts it as such (Buzan, Wæver, and De Wilde 1998).

The existing theoretical discussions of securitisation theory have predominantly focused on individual aspects of the idea of theory, such as the role of identity and identification (Bill McSweeney 1996; B. McSweeney 1999), ethics (Floyd 2021), audience (Wertman and Kaunert 2022; Côté 2016; Leonard and Kaunert 2010) and securitisation in non-democratic environments (Vuori 2016, 2008). However, the realist approach has equated security with the security of a state, focusing on operating territorial borders and providing physical safety to the population (Hama 2017). This approach views states as insecure due to the global struggle marked by using power, military force and realpolitik (Paul et al. 2021). Thus, the survival of the fittest states takes precedence without considering their sociocultural differences (Rendall 2022; Mearsheimer 2014).

In examining the security aspect of Pakistan, this study regards security as a social construct. Waseem (2006, 103) argues that Pakistan has “centralization of power at the cost of provincial autonomy, securitisation of the national vision, use of ideology to subvert the process of articulation of regional or class interests and a discouragement of the politics of issues in favour of the politics of identity.” An alternative way to explain securitisation in Pakistan, moving from traditional security to a nontraditional security paradigm, is through the Human Security approach. This approach emphasizes the ‘people-centric’ concept of security, challenging the dichotomy of freedom from want and fear. It advocates prioritizing human development as the state's and society's central focus. In today's geo-economics, the significance of human development has increased. Despite domestic instability and mounting international pressure, Pakistan is gradually transitioning from a traditional security perspective to a nontraditional one, strongly supported by all major stakeholders and now a core element of National Security Policy 2022 (Ashraf, Mustafa, and Ali 2023).

The securitisation theory offers a critical lens to understand Pakistan's developmental challenges. Specifically, the application of securitisation theory clarifies the nation's struggle to foster development and deliver essential services to counter extremism, thereby addressing the factors contributing to its classification as a fragile state. This multifaceted analytical approach sheds light on the complex interplay between security concerns and developmental policies, emphasizing the need for comprehensive

strategies to overcome limitations imposed by prevailing security paradigms

Integration of Security-Development in Policy

The dominance of Pakistan's security apparatus in civilian affairs precedes the country's development needs (Aziz 2009; A. Shah 2014). In its pursuit of dominance, there is growing apprehension that the military obstructs and frequently ignores the necessary conditions for progress and growth. As a result, there is a discrepancy in the relationship between security and development. It is argued that achieving sustainable peace hinges on addressing fundamental security and development challenges and that issues such as poverty, internal conflicts, complex emergencies, and human insecurity are interconnected. Post-cold War, amid the fragile states, the global liberal peacebuilding agenda prioritized security and development, relying on democratization, free market economies, the rule of law, and societal integration to promote global security and peace, which gave rise to the idea of the Security-Development nexus (Richmond 2011; Donais and Knorr 2013).

The overemphasis of the military on Pakistani nationalism, despite having a heterogenous and diverse population, to prove her regional importance against the more prominent India has led to an excess focus on security and the loss of socioeconomic development of her citizens. Consequently, Pakistan is seen to have failed democratic institutions, security prioritized over development policy and a security-focused foreign policy, shunning regional integration (Yusuf 2013). Defense spending accounted for eighty-five per cent of the central government's income in the first years after the partition (Hasan 1997, 366). The allocation of more than seventy per cent of the country's budget in her initial years (Haqqani 2016, 9) to security spending created a disastrous precedent for future policymakers, who have continued prioritizing military spending above development. This pattern has continued in successive regimes (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Percentage of GDP spending

Source World Bank: World Development Indicators; SIPRI Military Expenditure Database.

The campaign to increase defense spending has persisted, demonstrating the military and civil bureaucracies' dominance over policymaking. The lack of finances invested in areas such as health and education only confirms Pakistan's lack of attention to its people and their needs, and the country's continued fall down the human development index demonstrates the developmental cost (Table 1 and Figure 2). Increasing defense and security-related spending compared to allocation towards social services such as health and education further demonstrates the problems in Pakistan's political economy

and the security-oriented approach of policymakers.

Table 1 Human Development Index – Pakistan (2022)

Indicator	Value
Life expectancy at birth (years)	66.4
Expected years of schooling	7.9
Mean years of schooling	4.4
Gross national income (GNI) per capita (USD)	5,374
GNI per capita rank minus HDI rank	-27
HDI rank (2021)	165
HDI Rank (2022)	164

Source UNDP (2024, 276)

Figure 2 HDI Ranking of Pakistan

Source UNDP Human Development Index Reports (various editions)

Securitisation of State: Pakistan's experience

In the conventional sense, security corresponds to a state's ability to preserve its territory in opposition to external aggressors. There are four interrelated layers of security: individual (person), national (state), regional, and global, and their interdependence makes it impossible to address the security of the state if security at any of the other levels has been compromised (Suleri 2010). Countries with potent defense forces are considered more secure than those with weak militaries. A recent discussion on state safety considers non-traditional sections more concerned with human security than a state's territorial safety (Biswas and Murai 2024; Lahiry 2020). Pakistan's experience engaging with threats is based on the military's threat assessment (Staniland, Mir, and Lalwani 2018). In the analysis of the security situation in Pakistan, there are two schools of thought (Ahmar 1997). One school suggests the presence of a strong, well-equipped, and capable military to counter any threat, domestic or international, especially where volatile borders are concerned. A strong military offers

a strong response and ensures survival in a volatile neighborhood (Snyder 1984; A. Shah 2014). Another school argues that the security of any country depends on its human capital. Therefore, countries with better human development indices are better equipped to handle internal or external pressure (UNDP 2024). The argument goes further that without political stability, economic development and social harmony among the citizens, the country will need the military to defend it (Ahmar 1997).

Since independence, the leaders of Pakistan have chosen to go with a strong military and to work on human development at a later stage, which has led to the belief that the military is crucial to the country's life and prosperity. In the absence or low-key presence of democratic and civilian control, the country's security apparatus holds sway and creates a pseudo-state with a narrative for the benefit of the security apparatus (Shah, 2014; Nawaz, 2008). Pakistan's security through its military is run by the Roman expression 'Salus republican est suprema lex' (Safety of the State is the supreme law), often taking actions, whose legality is questionable (Nawaz, 2008).

As the state's bulwark, the military's well-being precedes human development. This has led to the involvement of armed forces in almost all sectors of the public sphere and has created a corporate identity (Siddiqi 2017) the armed forces are a uniting force that primarily promotes the welfare of its members¹ and serves as a mediator between domestic and international policy (Nawaz, 2008).

Applying the securitisation theory in Pakistan's perspective, this study argues that the state (read military) considers India and extremists a threat to its existence. The message conveyed to the public (audience) is that Pakistan, the 'fortress of Islam', is under threat of extremist ideology supported by anti-state elements and the hidden hand of enemies. Countering that threat requires the public to support the military, and extraordinary measures should be supported if needed by the military. Pakistan, in response to the terrorist and extremist threat, defined militant in military terms² and granted powers to the military for preventive detention.³ This was in addition to the Security of Pakistan Act of 1952 and the Anti-Terrorism Act of 1997. Public support for Zarb-e Azab was overwhelming due to the positive image building of the military's media wing (Dawn 2014). In the wake of the Army Public School massacre, the legislature passed the Twenty-first Amendment unopposed, allowing for the establishment of a special military court for two years for trials of incarcerated terrorism suspects (Dawn 2015).⁴ Chughtai (2015) mentions phases in which the military has weaponized the security discourse. In the first phase (1947-58), the military promoted a zeal for social welfare despite having a larger share in the first few years. The second phase (1959-1976) promoted national unity and integrity sans Islam but had to revert to Islamic nationalism with the rise of Bengali separatism and the 1965 War with India. The military-mullah alliance or state-ulema alliance during the time of Yahya Khan was to counter the Bengali Nationalism of Sheikh Mujeeb-ur-Rehman⁵ (Haqqani, 2005). The third phase

¹ Total number of active Military personnel is 660,000 (Army 560,000 Navy 30,000 Air 70,000) Gendarmerie & Paramilitary 291,000 (IISS 2024, 301)

² Section 2 sub-section 2 (f) of The Protection of Pakistan Act, 2014. Available at <https://pakistancode.gov.pk/pdf/files/administrator245b4aa097578e1179807a9c9e6f7a30.pdf>

³ The Protection of Pakistan Act, 2014 Section 6, *ibid*.

⁴ From January 2015 to March 2019, 717 cases were referred for trials by the military courts, of which 646 were disposed of. 345 hardcore terrorists were sentenced to death, of which 56 were executed. 296 other convicts were sentenced to imprisonment on different terms, whereas five accused were acquitted.

⁵ Sheikh Mujibur Rahman (17 March 1920 – 15 August 1975), honorifically called *Bangabandhu* ('Friend of Bengal'), was a Bengali nationalist leader from East Pakistan. He was President of the Awami League when he announced his six points and started the Independence movement. He is

had been Islam in Military garb under Zia (1979-1988) but continued till Musharraf. Zia's Islamization provided military access to the public by playing with the sentiments of the public, allowing the spirit of armed conflict across borders to spread (Abbas 2015). The fourth phase, from 1999 to 2010, promoted an idea of Islamic society that was tolerant and comprehensive.

Musharraf tried modernising the country and its institutions through his 'Enlightened Moderation' moderation. It was a plan he presented to the international community and Muslim community. He proposed a plan to "shun militancy and extremism and adopt the path of socioeconomic uplift" (Musharraf 2004). He sought help from the West, especially the United States of America, to "resolve all political disputes with justice and to aid in the socioeconomic betterment of the deprived Muslim world" (Musharraf 2004). His opposition came from the religious scholars and political parties who called his plan devoid of socio-cultural consideration. It was argued that enlightened moderation did not "emanate from our own socio-cultural milieu, our own traditions, values or requirements" (Ahmad 2004, 1).

The developmental challenges faced by Pakistan are discussed in Chapter Four. However, this study argues that the securitisation of the State has been used to enhance its military prowess, but this premise has its challenges, which are explained below.

External security challenges and concerns:

Ishtiaq Ahmed (2013) is of the view that Pakistan's security has been conditioned by two main hostile forces, both bordering it – India, Pakistan's main enemy and Afghanistan, which adversaries have frequently ruled. Pakistan's military's overriding concern with India has led to the creation of a 'Security State Syndrome' (Husain 2019a). The casting of India as the archenemy has allowed Pakistan to develop a reactionary model where any incident of terrorism can easily be blamed on India for destabilizing the country. It also provides an easy way to appear as the victim to the outside world. Pakistan's focus on keeping India at bay has pitted both countries against each other, and for the past decade, they have accused each other of state-sponsored terrorism. This hysteria has often led Pakistan to avoid having a meaningful dialogue with India, and fueled by religious fervor, Pakistan's dependence on the army remained undiminished. As early as 1964, Khalid Bin Sayeed declared, "Almost every action of Pakistan can be interpreted as being motivated by fear of India" (Sayeed 1964, 746).

Looking at the north-western and north-eastern provinces of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Punjab gives Pakistan's security and strategic planning much more importance than other public goods. On the east lies India or Hindustan. Indo-Pak relations have gone through four Wars (in three, Kashmir was the central theme, and one was in East Pakistan). Disputed Jammu and Kashmir has been the main point of the start of dialogue for peace, and since the abolition of the special status of Jammu and Kashmir, this relationship has been cold.

On its western border, Afghanistan with its claim of lands comprising Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (including the Tribal areas).⁶ The Afghan-Pakistan border has been porous, allowing for the cross-border movement of people and goods. Every Afghan government since 1947 has rejected the Durand Line, and Pakistan erected a fence to limit and control the movement of people and goods but also manage border crossings. This fencing has been made controversial, and even the Taliban have complained (Mir, Olson, and Watkins 2022).

On the foreign policy front, Pakistan has always followed the garrison state, and her

considered the founding father of Bangladesh and held positions as its president or prime minister until his assassination in 1975.

support of elements aligning with her interests has been noted, whether it has been the support of the Taliban in Afghanistan or the Kashmiri freedom fighters. Ironically, Pakistan has also forged a close relationship with the Western World, most notably with the United States of America. Pakistan has not only been in the capital bloc in the fight against communism and a non-NATO ally in the War on Terror. Her membership in security bodies, such as the Southeast Asia Treaty Organization (SEATO) and the Central Treaty Organization (CENTO), granted access to increasingly sophisticated weapons and financial aid.

Pakistan recognized China despite it being a Socialist state. Since its independence, the Sino-Pak relationship has been strong and has acted as a counter to the strategic partnership between the United States of America and India. Both the US and India have antagonistic relationships with China. Pakistan has depended on China for support on the international stage, and the Chinese government's Belt and Road Initiative's Pakistani part, the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor, is a testament to both countries' cooperation in trade. However, through its military, Pakistan maneuvers the complex situation where it seeks only benefits from both allies without meddling much in their collision on the international stage.

Acting as a guardian of two holy houses, Pakistan provides military support and personnel to the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, with its good ties with states in the Middle East, Pakistan's military leverages its position to tackle any challenge it faces.

State of Internal Security

On the domestic front, Pakistan's involvement in providing security to its citizens is dwarfed by many factors: ethnic discords, separatist movements, economic woes, sectarianism, and intolerance leading to extremism. Its police and law enforcement agencies are modelled on the para-military security system, which functions as "a public-frightening organisation, not a public-friendly agency" (Suddle 2003, 23). The domestic law enforcement agencies of federal and provincial governments have overlapping functions such as investigation, intelligence gathering, crime prevention, and maintenance of law and order.

The federal government has specialized departments such as the Federal Investigation Agency (investigates blue-collar crimes and crimes against state interests), Frontier Constabulary, Pakistan Rangers (border security force), and Pakistan Coast Guards (coastal security), to name a few. Despite having an old traditional policing mechanism established by the British empire, little has been changed, and the government has placed the responsibility on the police to tackle threats and violence presented by armed extremist groups and organized crime associated with the arms and drug trades and land-grabbing. Institutional restrictions that have long plagued the police—such as limited personnel and financial resources, poor infrastructure, issues in the criminal justice system, and meddling and influence from internal and foreign sources—have experienced no significant improvements (HRW 2016).

All these challenges jeopardize the Pakistani police's capacity to implement law and order, follow human rights, and be free of corruption and undue influence. The same issues have been translated into the former FATA, where the British system had a different arrangement. The local leadership, Malik (leader), a hereditary title, and the district administration headed by the Political Agent under the so-called draconian law of Frontier Crime Regulation, 1901 would provide internal security. The local police (khasadar) were manned by the young men provided by the Maliks, and their local knowledge would be used. The district administration would have Levies, a para-military militia, to aid the local police. This system allowed for a crime-free FATA. The system was so effective that Tehrik Taliban Pakistan started to target the Maliki system

and eventually took over not only the local conflict resolution and mediation mechanism but local security as well, leading to Pakistan sending their troops into FATA and later military operations were conducted where the civil administration was severely hampered (Naseer 2015; Shahzad 2011). The TTP used the same tactic in Swat and Malakand agency with the aid of the local population, where the influential local leadership was targeted. The provincial government in KP countered the strategy by encouraging local Peoples Peace Committees and equipped them covertly to fight against the rogue elements among the population. However, this system backfired, and instead of controlling the Taliban incursion, it proved to be ineffective in Swat and Malakand, eventually requiring the military to establish its presence.

As a result of military operations against the extremist elements in Swat and Waziristan from 2007 onwards, the phenomenon of internally displaced persons was seen where over one million citizens were displaced from their homes and placed in temporary camps (Orakzai, 2012) in addition to the Afghan refugees in Pakistan since 1979. The International Crisis Group (2010, p.1) observed, "If military objectives dictate rehabilitation and reconstruction efforts, a population exhausted by conflict could become a soft target for militants, making stability in the northwest even more elusive." Such conditions created socio-economic and political challenges, such as providing food, shelter, sanitation, protection of women and children, resettlement of internally displaced persons, and the relationship between the hosts and internally displaced persons (Orakzai, 2012).

Despite law and order and local government being under the provincial governments, the Federal Government still manages and controls Pakistan's internal security. Provinces have developed their Counter Terrorism Departments, which conduct intelligence-based operations. However, these operations are only done with the assistance and knowledge of the federal government and security agencies under the federal government. Provinces have been unable to draft their counterterrorism policies, especially Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, where Federally Administrated Tribal Areas were merged to form Tribal Districts. The Khyber Pakhtunkhwa government tried to present an alternative think tank to the National Counter Terrorism Authority, a Centre of Excellence on Counter Violent Extremism (KP Govt ACT, Tribune, 2022). Punjab has yet to act on its own counterterrorism and extremism policy. Also, Punjab has been mentioned as the birthplace of jihadi outfits operating in the name of an Islamic state, and the presence of many of these groups mentioned in the UN list of terror organisations at the heart of Punjab rings alarm bells (UN 2023).

Conclusion:

The overemphasis of the state on security and the disregard shown for human development has led the extremist ideology to present itself as the alternative and allowed the citizens to question the motives of the government planning machinery. The relationship between the federal government and other tiers of the government, although it seems to be working, is, in fact, due to the fiscal leverage of the federal government instead of the mutual coordination and cooperation, as it should be. Another point to mention here is that local governance if allowed to function as envisaged, would allow a better plan and policy to approach the local level, which would help eradicate not only the gap in development but also extremism. This has been argued that Pakistan's security apparatus manages not only to secure the country's borders but also secures its internal security too. This is the reason that Pakistani leadership has relied on the military men to take care when they are unable to do it by themselves.

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